

Electrical-Heating Molding Process Based on Carbon Fiber Felt for Fabricating Glass Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composite

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Abstract:

Traditional molding processes are generally based on external source heating with long molding time and high energy loss. Herein, the method of electrical-heating molding on thermoplastic composite is proposed to shorten molding cycle and improve the utilization of energy. Wet papermaking technology was applied to fabricate short carbon fiber felt with areal density of 15g/m^2 , thickness of $110\ \mu\text{m}$ and square resistance of $7\sim 10\Omega$. Then the short carbon fiber felt with good uniformity was used as heating source to heat continuous glass fiber reinforced polypropylene (PP) for fabricating thermoplastic composite. The results show that electrical-heating molding process is rapid and effective. Short carbon fibers are well infiltrated by PP, and PP cannot flow into glass fiber bundles under low pressure.

1. Introduction

Thermoplastic composite is widely applied in aviation, aerospace and transportation industry, owing to its excellent properties, such as high mechanical property, low density, good formability and recyclability^[1, 2]. Traditional molding processes, such as hot-press forming, pultrusion, filament winding and autoclave process, have been used for fabricating continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites^[3]. However, these molding processes are generally based on external source heating, in which the heat is transferred from external environment to internal material with long molding time and high energy loss. Therefore, developing new heating method to shorten molding cycle, improve the utilization of energy and reduce manufacturing cost is very essential. In the method of electrical-heating molding, thermoplastic matrix will flow above melting point heated by resistance current, and will harden after cooling down. Electrical heating method has fast heating speed and high utilization ratio of

energy, which could directly transfer heat from resistance to matrix without needing external environment^[4,5].

In this study, short carbon fiber felts with areal density of 15 g/m² and fiber length of 6 mm were fabricated, resistance measurement was used to characterize the uniformity of carbon felts. Then, these self-made carbon felts were used as electric heating source to manufacture continuous glass fiber reinforced polypropylene thermoplastics composites, and pressure was provided through a vacuuming procedure. Carbon felt was sandwiched in prepreg stack and was electrified to produce heat. The conditions (such as heating rate, forming temperature, holding time and cooling rate) were dominated by adjusting voltage, firstly, matrix quickly melted with high voltage at the heating stage, then voltage reduced to keep constant temperature in a certain time for joining matrix with carbon fibers and glass fibers, lastly, composite molded at lower voltage or cooled by water cooling system. Impregnation quality and resin distribution were used to analyze forming quality.

2. Experimental details

2.1 Materials

Short Carbon fibers with length of 6mm were used in this study: SYT49 T700 12K carbon fibers (Guangzhou Saiao Carbon fiber Company). Carbon fiber felts with areal density of 15g/m² were fabricated by laboratory prepared handsheet former. Hydroxyethylcellulose with 30000m.Pa.s was used for dispersant (Qingdao Yousuo Chemical Technology Co., Ltd). Fatty alcohol was used for defoamer (Jiangsu Hai'an petrochemical plant). Distilled water was provided by Beihang University. Continuous glass fiber reinforced polypropylene (CGFPP) with density of 1.50g/cm³, fiber content of 60wt%, tape thickness of 0.3mm, tape area weight of 450g/m², temperature of deflection under load of 149°C, thermal conductivity (through plane) of 0.4W/mk (Guangzhou Kingfa). Thin copper sheet with thickness of 0.1mm (Biling Company). Polytetrafluoroethylene film with thickness of 0.1mm (Shenzhen Hongyida Rubber shop) was used for vacuum bag.

2.2 Preparation of Carbon fiber felt

Wet papermaking technology was applied to fabricate short carbon fiber felt. Firstly, short carbon fibers were put into Soxhlet extractor to wash out sizing agent with acetone, to enhance the dispersibility of short carbon fibers in water. Then short carbon fibers, hydroxyethylcellulose and fatty alcohol were dispersed in distilled

water with a mass ratio of $m_{\text{(short carbon fibers)}}:m_{\text{(hydroxyethylcellulose)}}:m_{\text{(fatty alcohol)}}:m_{\text{(distilled water)}} = 1:4:2:2000$. The above solution was blended in high speed stirring rate range with magnetic stirrer for about 15h-20h at room temperature to obtain uniformly dispersed aqueous solution with short carbon fibers. Secondly, the aqueous solution was mixed with water in the handsheet former to fabricate short carbon fiber felt (SCFF). Self-made SCFF was dried at 100°C for 1hour in oven, then was put in the styrene acrylic emulsion for 1 min to obtain SCFF bonded together with glue content of 5%, area density of $15\text{g}/\text{m}^2$, diameter of 170mm, thickness of $110\ \mu\text{m}$, which was displayed in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Self-made short carbon fiber felt

2.3 Fabrication of Composite

Straight edge was used as a guide, CGFPP and SCFF were trimmed to size of 120 mm in length and 110 mm in width. Thin copper sheet was used as electrode, which was tailored to size of 100 mm in length and 5 mm in width. The layup configuration

was one SCFF layer inserted in the middle of six CGFPP layers, the direction of glass fiber is along with the direction of current flow, and two electrodes were placed at both sides of SCFF, as presented in Fig. 2(a). The schematic of the electrical heating system were displayed in Fig. 2(b).

Fig. 2 (a) Layup configuration of CGFPP, SCFF and electrodes; (b) schematic of the electrical heating system: 1.Direct current; 2.Heat shield; 3.Vacuum bag; 4.Breather; 5.Vacuum pump; 6.Thin aluminum sheet; 7.CGFPP; 8.Electrode; 9.SCFF; 10.Thermocouple; 11.Temperature recorder

2.4 Characterization

The morphologies of composite were measured by a scanning electron microscope (SEM, CamScan Inc. Apollo 300) under acceleration voltage of 15 kV. The cross-sections of composite structures were observed by optical microscopy (BX51M, Olympus Inc., Japan) The sample thickness was measured by micrometer caliper. The temperature distribution was measured by an infrared thermal imager (Fotric 226-3S, $-20^{\circ}\text{C} \sim 650^{\circ}\text{C}$). The resistance of SCFF was obtained by an resistance tester (TH2512, Changzhou Tonghui Electronics Co., Ltd). The direct current is provided by Agilent DC power supply (U8002A, 0~30V, 5A). To acquire the melting point of CGFPP was studied by differential scanning calorimetry (Mettler DSC I).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Physical and electrical-heating properties of SCFF

Real time temperature distribution image of SCFF was measured by the electrical heating system displayed in Fig. 3. SCFF was compressed by uniformly distributed pressure of 0.05MPa, which was provided by a vacuum pump. The DC power supply was used for heating SCFF. The polyimide foam board could effectively reduce the energy loss. Infrared thermal imager was used for measuring temperature distribution of SCFF. The temperature distribution image of SCFF was presented in Fig. 4. Fig. 4(a) and (b) show us that temperature distribution of SCFF is uniformly, and Fig. 4(c) and (d) display that the temperature fluctuation of two line segments(ab and cd) are less than 10°C , which illustrates that the self-made SCFF with excellent uniformity.

The square resistance^[6] of SCFF was measured at the same pressure condition as

Fig. 3 shown. By contrast, DC power supply was replaced by an resistance tester. The results of square resistance are listed in Tab. 1. It illustrates that the SCFFs with stable molding quality, which is in accordance with Fig.4.

Table 1 Square resistance of self-made SCFF

Sequence number of SCFF	Resistance \square in the x direction/ Ω	Resistance \square in the y direction/ Ω
1	8.54	8.96
2	8.75	9.16
3	9.66	9.48

Fig. 3 Schematic of SCFF electrical heat system: 1. Computer; 2. Vacuum pump; 3. Infrared thermal imager; 4. DC power supply; 5. Aluminum plate; 6. Sealant; 7. Vacuum bag; 8. Electrode; 9. Polyimide foam board; 10. SCFF; 11. Data line; 12. Air tube; 13. Power cord.

Fig. 4 Temperature distribution images of SCFF: (a) plane distribution graph; (b) three dimensional distribution map; (c) temperature fluctuation of ab segment; (d) temperature fluctuation of cd segment.

3.2 Melting property of CGFPP

Typical DSC curve was for recording the changes of heat flow per unit mass as a function of temperature. Thus, it was used to describe the consumption characteristics of heat during the overall thermal process^[7]. Herein, the DSC curve of CGFPP was tested by differential scanning calorimetry under the heating rates of 10°C/min. As shown in Fig.5, the peak temperature of endothermic peak in the graph is 164°C, which is the melting temperature of PP.

Fig. 5 DSC curve of CGFPP

3.3 Molding quality of composites

The electrical heating system were assembled by reference to Fig. 2. Then electrical heating process was carried on according to Fig. 5. This process consists of three periods, the temperature rising period, the constant temperature period, the cooling period. Temperature rises from room temperature to 190°C with heating rate of 33°C/min, then is kept at 190°C for 3min, in the end, decreases to room temperature with cooling rate of 33°C/min. Pressure of 0.1MPa is maintained from the start to the end.

Fig. 6 Temperature and pressure schedules of electrical heating vacuuming molding

As displayed in Fig. 7, the composite sample was firstly cut perpendicular to the direction of glass fibers, then, polished with sand paper and polishing cloth. At last, the samples were observed by optical microscopy. Fig. 7(a) presents that carbon fiber are well infiltrated by PP resin. Otherwise, Fig. 7(b) shows that poor infiltrated part exists in the center of the glass fiber bundle, PP resin cannot infiltrate in the glass fiber bundles well. This mainly due to PP resin has a higher viscosity at 190°C, it cannot flow into the center of glass fiber bundles under low pressure of 0.1MPa. Thus, higher pressure is needed in order to fabricate high quality composites.

Fig. 7 Optical micrographs of composite

Herein, the composite was split along with the carbon fiber layer, the surface morphology of carbon fiber was showed in Fig. 8. It can be seen from Fig. 8 (a) and (b) that a great of PP bulks are left on the surface of carbon fibers, this illustrates that carbon fiber and PP have built excellent interfacial adhesion after electrical heating process. Fig. 8 (c) and (d) show that lots of PP bulks are left on the surface of glass fibers, by contrast, Fig. 8 (e) and (f) show that few PP bulks are left on the surface of glass fibers. This reveals that poor interfacial adhesion between glass fibers and PP. Combine Fig.7(b), PP has a poor infiltration degree to glass fibers under low pressure.

Fig. 8 SEM images of surface morphology: (a) and (b) of carbon fibers bonded with PP, (c) and (d) of glass fibers bonded with PP, (e) and (f) of glass fiber bonded without PP

4. Conclusions

- (1) The established method of electrical heating process is rapid and effective.
- (2) The self-made short carbon fiber felt possesses good quality and uniformity.
- (3) Carbon fibers are well infiltrated by PP under electrical-heating molding process, and high pressure is needed for ensuring good infiltration of PP into glass fiber bundles.

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